

USING INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TECHNOLOGY IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article examines the genre-specific features of autobiographical works. Annotation. The article analyzes the use of modern technologies together with innovative methods and technologies in studying the Russian language. The subject of the study is teaching the Russian language to students of non-philological universities. From this point of view, the problem of learning a foreign language on the basis of innovative methods and technology, which helps self-development, seems extremely interesting and this is relevant when teaching the Russian language

Keywords: Russian language, innovative methods and technologies, online and offline learning, modern pedagogical technologies, philological universities

1 INTRODUCTION

The issue of using innovative technologies in the teaching process in the education system of Uzbekistan and in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language in particular seems particularly relevant in recent decades due to the increase in the general technical level of support, the development of the methodology itself, which is constantly in search of the most effective, accessible methods, techniques, methods of teaching aimed at “achieving the maximum possible mutual understanding in a multipolar world” [2].

“The current stage in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language can be characterized by such words as innovation, development, movement forward” [1]. This definition leads to the idea that innovations and productive changes, new methods and technologies are currently appearing in education, which can help improve the effectiveness of classes, as well as ways to evaluate their results.

If we talk about innovations in educational technologies, then, first of all, it is also necessary to provide a definition that explains what exactly is included in this concept. According to V.G. Kolosova, “innovative technologies are a set of methods, means and activities that ensure innovative activity” [3]. The term “innovative technologies in vocational education” refers to “technologies focused on the formation of systematic creative technical thinking of students and their ability to generate non-standard technical ideas when solving creative production problems” (Scientific Electronic Library).

Among the variety of technologies, the following can be distinguished:

- learning in collaboration;
- design technologies (project method);
- tandem method;

- case study technology;
- “edutainment” technology,
- distance learning;
- computer teaching technologies;
- gaming learning technologies, etc.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of innovative technologies is possible not only as a way to transfer material to students, organize distance learning of a language, testing, etc., but is also a useful source for the teacher himself. These can be ready-made resources: reference, open educational resources, simulators; or services for developing materials and organizing training: services for creating educational materials, test designer, classroom management, etc.

Thus, in the practice of working in educational institutions, the pressing problem of the day is the education of a socially active person who is capable of taking responsibility for independently made decisions. For graduates of secondary and higher educational institutions, the requirements of readiness for orientation in a life saturated with information flows and for continuous self-learning have become mandatory. Using a communication network: e-mail, the Internet or Zoom, television, etc. in learning foreign languages is the norm today. In this regard, the use and improvement of methods of the educational process and educational technologies is of particular importance. This is especially true for the field of studying Russian as a foreign language, where interaction with the teacher in the classroom cannot be effective without students independently mastering the necessary vocabulary. In the context of this study, such innovative methods as listening and speaking are of particular interest.

Listening skills can become stable if the student independently improves them outside of class time or by reinforcing the materials covered, especially during

online learning. This can be facilitated by means of information and communication technologies that allow you to hear the speech of native Russian speakers, see educational information via a computer, provide immediate feedback between a student at a non-philological university and a teaching tool, as well as organize educational activities at an individual pace and monitor the results of assimilation. The success of mastering vocabulary in the Russian language is determined by many objective and subjective factors, among which the degree to which students have developed the psychological mechanisms of listening (hearing skills) and speaking (pronunciation skills) is of particular importance; awareness of one's own language learning goals, frequency of listening, etc.

Problems of listening comprehension are widely covered in scientific and methodological literature. Psychologists, linguists and methodologists recognize this innovative method as the most difficult type of activity, therefore, work on developing the skill of perceiving vocabulary or speaking by ear requires painstaking efforts. In this regard, the approach of foreign methodologists such as Jim Skriviner, Larsen-Freeman and S.L. attracts attention. McKay's approach to listening, which is based on a comparison of listening mechanisms in native speakers and learners of a new language. The student immediately becomes a listener, like a child - just after being born, but after only months he begins to speak, and he will learn to read and write only after a few years [2]. This means that auditing skills are primary and form the basis for the formation of all other speech skills and abilities. This leads to the fact that for a student of Russian as a foreign language, both the process of special training in listening, acquired during training and improved independently, and the need to know one's natural abilities for self-learning to understand foreign language speech by ear are important; in this case, the role of innovative technologies and methods is enormous. For example, you can invite students from non-philological universities to compare works with film adaptations, find similarities and differences, come up with questions and interactive games based on the content of the work. This method allows us to reveal the sequence of development of the logic of assimilation and application of acquired knowledge. Based on the material of a work of fiction and a film adaptation, such planning involves covering the historical, cultural and nationally specific context in each lesson. In addition, in our opinion, comparison (comparative studies) can be combined with the method of critical thinking, which includes three stages: Challenge - Comprehension - Reflection. So, when comparing, you can use the following types of

work: historical excursion, reconstruction of historical events, designing a family tree, costume ball, cultural commentary, poetry evening, meeting in a poetry cafe, debate on aesthetic issues. This is the first stage - Challenge. It allows you to interest students, arouse sustained interest in the topic being studied, and generalize existing knowledge. The second stage allows you not only to comprehend the information obtained during the analysis process, but also to correlate it with existing knowledge. The third stage involves the formulation of theoretical conclusions based on the analysis of the literary text and film adaptation, thus identifying the similarities and differences between them, taking into account the individual author's layers and comparing the results of experiments, as well as observations. Thus, the Reflection stage makes it possible to summarize the information received and to form in students a holistic understanding of the film adaptation based on a work of art as a fact of literary heritage.

Thus, speech hearing is one of the most important mental mechanisms. It involves the ability to isolate, discriminate, and recognize differentiated features of perceived content. Next, long-term memory is turned on, stored samples are compared with the information received, mental operations come into play, which leads to an awareness of the meaning of the audible text. The basis of audit information is made up of parallel operating psychological processes - perception at the level of words, sentences, dialogue, and understanding, the result of semantic processing of audio information, generates the student's communicative intention, the logic of thought. Modern methodologists note that background information has a significant impact on the ability of memory to retain coherent texts, so associative connections arise already at the stage of familiarization with the title of the text. Reading is formed at the stage of perception of graphic images, and with the help of pronunciation, auditory-motor images of words are recreated. Speaking is built adequately to the communication process, with a priority role given to improving the skills and abilities of oral speech (speaking and listening).

When reading aloud, students improve their auditory and pronunciation skills, accumulate experience in perceived sound images in a stream of coherent speech, relationships between concepts, and reading fluency. In order to make the listening process of students studying Russian as a foreign language successful, it is necessary to develop a system of training exercises aimed at maximizing the activation of natural mechanisms. And in this case, the innovative "Round up" method this modern and innovative method belongs to famous

American teachers, methodologists and psychologists J. Dewey and W. Kilpatrick, proposed it in the study of English as a foreign language, and we can use it in Russian language classes as a foreign language is most productive and will be of interest to students of non-philological universities when studying Russian as a foreign language. Unlike classical forms, innovative pedagogical technologies help overcome the fear of failure, and also seem promising in terms of developing the creative self-expression of students at non-philological universities.

Such conditions allow you to vary approaches to listening and individualize this process. This can be facilitated by modern pedagogical technologies together with innovative methods and technologies, one of which is the universal multimedia interactive complex “listening + reading + speaking” based on the “Round up” method, designed to form and improve pronunciation and memorize new words that contribute to the development of students' speech skills. As the linguistic content of the training, subject-semantic and lexico-grammatical content is presented, the logic of which allows you to diversify methodological techniques that ensure the formation of skills and abilities in listening, reading, and speaking. The most extensive component of this method is vocabulary, which helps to perceive authentic speech. Regardless of how well a student speaks grammar and the phonetic side of speech, the student is successfully preparing for communication, and this innovative method allows the use of various forms of learning.

3 CONCLUSIONS

On the linguistic simulator, the student can exercise self-control of pronunciation; the student can record any word or phrase or rules for constructing sentences in his performance and compare it with the sound of the speaker's voice. Thus, the process of studying Russian as a foreign language, students of non-philological universities not only comprehend the way of expressing thoughts, but also perceive the language as a source of information about the national culture of the people, since the language is a sign of the nation, expresses the national culture of the people who speak it, we believe that innovative methods and technologies are relevant during online or offline learning.

Thus, the research topic is relevant for the current stage of development of pedagogical science. There is a gap between the need for methods that allow the formation of a lexical minimum for students at non-philological universities and the insufficient development of this topic in the specialized literature. There are several opinions regarding the necessary pedagogical conditions for the formation of the lexical

minimum of students (especially students who are not philologists). To activate the formation of speech among students of non-philological universities, it is necessary to use something new, interesting, and non-standard, this contributes to the development of students' cognitive interest in learning and a more solid assimilation of knowledge. Modern pedagogical technologies in parallel with innovative methods and technologies in teaching Russian as a foreign language to students of non-philological universities can act as such a means.

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